

Examples of Unethical Behaviors related to IT and IS

Author: [Eltigani Musa](#)

Introduction

In the recent years, debates on ethical use of information systems have been emerging due to lack the poor use of information systems (Joseph, 2011). Issues related to software piracy, plagiarism, spoofing and hacking are reported daily in this era of information age. Information systems have played vital roles in enhancing business operations and facilitating communication to take place. Nevertheless, advancements in information technology have been contributing to increased unethical issues in the business world. (Mason, 2015) , defines unethical practices in information systems as the process of using information systems to manipulate people’s privacy, integrity of information and denial of access to information system resources. In the discussions below, we discuss two reports of unethical practice on information systems.

Apple’s Controversial Use of Information Technology (McLaughlin, 2014)

Apple Inc. is worldwide known technology firm that has been on the forefront of information technology in developing new products for the international market. Ethical issues in the organization started when a client named, Adrienne Moore sued the vendor for allegedly tweaking a phone she had bought from them from receiving text messages that were sent from Android smartphones. According to (Mason, 2015), ethical issues that organizations are supposed to observe when it comes to information systems are; ensuring information is private and confidential, enhancing availability and integrity to information. Apples move of blocking a customer’s phone from accepting messages sent over from an android phone is an unethical behavior as it prevents information availability.

(Sloan, 2011), says that Apples move to block messages from sent from other devices to the customer's phone was a plan to ensure that the company was able to increase sales on its products. He adds that the complaint was not only heard from one person, but from multiple clients who were comparing that they were not able to access the messages sent from other phones with different operating systems. Apple latter defended itself and said that the error was caused by a bug in the phone's applications and the company was on its way to fix the problem. Preventing one from accessing their personal information in this case is an unethical practice and organizations need to enhance accessibility of information at all times (Nayab, 2014).

Enron's Ethical Collapse (Johnson, 2013)

Enron Corporation was an American Energy company that was formed in 1985. At the time of its formation, the company was enjoying massive profits from this region in the world (Johnson, 2013). Technology was key aspect to this organization and it had invested heavily on acquiring state of the art technology. As years passed by, the corporation collapsed due to manipulation of information and bankruptcy. It was latter known that the organization was manipulating its records before auditors came in for auditing, and this process continued for a long time. The company was also reported to be monitoring their employees in terms of the resources and communication messages that they send to each other over the organization's network. Any organization is required to ensure that it does not interfere with its employees private information in any way possible (Mason, 2015).

Manipulation of data and information stored in any database without any approval conflicts with information system ethics (Sloan, 2011). One is required to have consent from all people involved before it can be changed. Enron's case was different here as the organization was mutilating accounting records to hide their unethical behaviors. The unethical behaviors witnessed in the organization led to the collapse of the organization in the latter years.

In conclusion, the various unethical practices in information systems that different organizations engage in have been identified in the above two discussions. Unethical practices within any organization have been seen to affect the way people relate to each other and has an overall effect of bringing down an organization. It is thus necessary for any organizations to ensure that it observes ethical use of its information systems.

References:

Johnson, C., 2013. Enron's Ethical Collapse: Lessons for Leadership Educators. *Unethical Practices in Information System* , 24(11), pp. 04-15.

Joseph, C., 2011. Unethical IS Behaviors Organizations. *Information System Ethics*, 45(23), pp. 23-35.

Mason, R. O., 2015. Four Ethical Issues of the Information Age. [Online]

Available at: <http://www.gdrc.org/info-design/4-ethics.html>

[Accessed 6th July 2016].

McLaughlin, K., 2014. Apple's Controversial use of information Technology. [Online]

Available at: <http://www.crn.com/slide-shows/channel-programs/300075198/the-10-most-controversial-companies-of-2014.htm/pgno/0/2?itc=refresh>

[Accessed 06 July 2016].

Nayab, N., 2014. Ethical Use of information Systems. *The Business Journal* , 12(23), pp. 34-45.

Sloan, A., 2011. *Information System Ethics*. 3rd ed. New York: Oxford Press.

Share this: